

Chlorhexidine in Endodontics

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Complete debridement and disinfection of the pulpal space are considered to be essential for predictable long-term success in endodontic treatment. Residual pulpal tissue, bacteria and dentin debris may persist in the irregularities of root canal systems, even after meticulous mechanical preparation. Irrigation is a critical component because irrigants can reach areas inaccessible to instruments. Therefore, several irrigating substances have been recommended for use in combination with canal preparation, including sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl), chlorhexidine gluconate, 17% EDTA, citric acid, MTAD and 37% phosphoric acid solution. However, if these substances remain in the root canal, they might affect the penetration of the resin sealer in dentin and its polymerization. They might also degenerate dentin if they have a negative effect on the collagen fibres. It has long been recognized that the antibacterial effects of chemo-mechanical procedures can be enhanced by the subsequent placement of an antimicrobial intracanal medication, particularly in those cases of exudation, haemorrhage, perforation, root resorption, trauma or incomplete root formation. Nevertheless, the efficacy of both procedures also depends on the vulnerability of the involved microbial species present in the root canal system. Moreover, in order to avoid re-infection of the cleansed space, not only the placement of a host-compatible root canal filling but also of a permanent coronal restoration must be performed.

Chlorhexidine has the unique property of substantivity and can be applied clinically as antimicrobial agent during all phases of the root canal preparation-

- Disinfection of the operatory field.
- During the enlargement of the canals orifices.

- Removal of necrotic tissues before performing the root canal length determination.
- In the chemo-mechanical preparation prior to the foraminal patency and enlargement.
- As an intracanal medicament alone or combined with other substances like calcium hydroxide.
- In the disinfection of obturation cones.
- In the removal of gutta-percha cones during retreatment.
- In the disinfection of prosthetic space, among others.

General Use

Chlorhexidine was registered in 1954 by the Imperial Chemical Industries Co. Ltd. of Macclesfield (United Kingdom) under the brand name Hibitane[®], the first internationally accepted antiseptic for cleaning skin, wounds and mucous membranes because of its strong affinity to such areas, with high level of antibacterial activity and low mammalian toxicity. In 1957, only 3 years after coming into the market, the broad antimicrobial spectrum of Chlorhexidine led to an extension of its indications to include not only skin disinfection, but also use in the fields of ophthalmology, urology, gynaecology and otorhino-laryngology. Although chlorhexidine started being used to control bacterial plaque in 1959, its use became widespread in dentistry only in the 1970s.

Chlorhexidine is currently considered the gold standard of oral antiseptics and is, along with fluoride, the most extensively researched preventive agent in dentistry. In addition to its effects on dental plaque and gingivitis, chlorhexidine is effective in the prevention and treatment of caries; secondary infections to oral surgical procedures, and in the maintenance of the health of peri-implant tissues. It also retains its activity in the presence of blood, wounds and burns.

Presentation Form

For endodontic purposes, chlorhexidine can be used in a liquid or in a gel presentation. Chlorhexidine gel consists of a gel base (1% natrosol, a hydroxyethylcellulose, pH 6-9) and chlorhexidine gluconate, in an optimal pH range of 5.5 to 7.0. Natrosol gel is a biocompatible carbon polymer that is a water-soluble substance, and therefore can be easily removed from the root canal with a final flush of distilled water. Some studies have shown that the antimicrobial activity of chlorhexidine liquid is equal or superior to that of chlorhexidine gel when the direct contact was used as a methodology. In other studies, using the agar diffusion test, 2% chlorhexidine gel was superior to 2% chlorhexidine liquid.

Ferraz et al showed that 2% chlorhexidine gel has several advantages over 2% chlorhexidine solution, in spite of having similar antimicrobial, substantivity and biocompatibility properties. The chlorhexidine gel lubricates the root canal walls, which reduces the friction between the file and the dentin surface, facilitating the instrumentation and decreasing the risks of instrument breakage inside the canal. In addition, by facilitating instrumentation, chlorhexidine gel improves the elimination of organic tissues, which compensates for its incapacity to dissolve them. Another advantage of chlorhexidine gel is the reduction of smear layer formation, which does not occur with the liquid form. Chlorhexidine gel maintains almost all the dentinal tubules open because its viscosity keeps the debris in suspension (rheological action), reducing smear layer formation. Furthermore, the gel formulation may keep the "active principle" of chlorhexidine in contact with the microorganisms for a longer time, inhibiting their growth.

It is important to point out that during chemo-mechanical preparation, before using each file, 1 ml of chlorhexidine gel is introduced in the root canal with a syringe (24-gauge needle or smaller) and immediately after each instrumentation, 5 ml of distilled water is used to irrigate the canal. Before the use of EDTA or other chemical substance, a final flush with 10 ml of distilled water is recommended in order to remove traces of chlorhexidine inside the root canals.

Storage

A shelf life of at least 1 year can be expected, provided that packaging is adequate, in a dark, refrigerated bottle. Regarding the gel formulation, it may keep its pH and satisfactory antimicrobial activity for approximately 10 months after the fabrication date.

Mechanism of Action

Chlorhexidine is a strong base and it is more stable in

the form of its salts. The salts originally employed were acetate and hydrochlorite, both of which suffer from relatively poor water solubility and were largely replaced by the digluconate in 1957, which is a highly water soluble salt. Aqueous solutions of chlorhexidine are more stable within the pH range from 5 to 8. The antimicrobial activity of chlorhexidine is pH-dependent, being the optimum range from 5.5 to 7.0, within which is the pH of body surfaces and tissues. It readily dissociates at the physiological pH, releasing the positively charged CH component.

The bactericidal effect of the drug is due to the cationic molecule binding to extra-microbial complexes and negatively charged microbial cell walls, thereby altering the osmotic equilibrium of the cells.

Antimicrobial Activity

Regarding the spectrum of activity, chlorhexidine is bactericidal and effective against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, facultative and strict anaerobes, yeasts and fungi, particularly *Candida albicans*. It is active against some viruses (respiratory viruses, herpes, cytomegalovirus, HIV) and inactive against bacterial spores at room temperature. It also retains its activity in the presence of blood and organic matters.

In the liquid presentation, chlorhexidine kills microorganisms in 30 seconds or less, while in the gel formulation it takes from 22 seconds (2% chlorhexidine gel) to 2 hours (0.2% chlorhexidine gel). Several in vitro works using a broth dilution test have shown that 2.0% chlorhexidine (in both presentation forms) and 5.25% sodium hypochlorite have similar antimicrobial performance against all tested microorganisms, while others have shown the superiority of 2% chlorhexidine gel or liquid over 5.25% Sodium hypochlorite using the agar diffusion method.

Clinical investigations have also been performed to compare the antimicrobial activity of chlorhexidine and sodium hypochlorite, and reported that these two substances had comparable effects in eliminating bacteria.

A clinical study, evaluated the degree of microbial reduction after chemo-mechanical preparation of human root canals containing necrotic pulp tissue when using two endodontic irrigating reagents, 5.25% sodium hypochlorite or 2% chlorhexidine gel. Assessment of the bacterial load was accomplished. The bacterial load was reduced substantially in both groups (over 96%). The bacterial reduction in the sodium hypochlorite-group was significantly greater ($p < 0.01$) than in the chlorhexidine-group, probably due to the differences between the mechanisms of action of sodium hypochlorite and chlorhexidine.

To be continued.....